

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES AND AEROBIC EXERCISE ON MUSCULAR STRENGTH SELF-CONCEPT AND BLOOD PRESSURE

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present study was to find the effect of yogic practice and aerobic exercise on self-confidence and blood pressure (both systolic and diastolic). For this purpose, forty five middle aged men of Uduppi town, Mangalore district, Karnataka state in the age group of 35 – 40 years were selected. They were divided into three equal groups (n = 15), each group consisted of fifteen subjects, in which group – I underwent yogic practice, group – II underwent aerobic exercise and group – III acted as control group who did not participate in any special training. The training period for this study was five days in a week for twelve weeks. Prior to and after the training period the subjects were tested for self-confidence and blood pressure (systolic and diastolic). Self-confidence was assessed by using Agnihotri self-confidence inventory (ASCI) and blood pressure was assessed by using sphygmomanometer respectively. The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to find out the significant difference if any, among the experimental groups and control group on selected criterion variables separately. Since there were three groups involved in this study the Scheffè S test was used as pos-hoc test. It was concluded from the result of the study that the yoga practice and aerobic exercise has positively altered the criterion variables, such as, self-confidence and blood pressure (both systolic and diastolic).

Key Words: Yogic Practice, Aerobic Exercise, Self-Confidence, Systolic & Diastolic Blood Pressure

Introduction:

This reality of pure Consciousness has been recognized by all thinkers, spiritualists or materialists, as the fundamental axiom of life from which intelligence, volition, love and thought emanate [1]. It is a science that affects not only the aware oneself but the subliminal as well. It is a practical physiological training, can praise man to the 'supra mundane level'. [2] Patanjali introduced yoga and its principles were first written down in India several thousand years ago.[3]

According to Swami Vishnu Devananda [4] "Yoga is not an ancient myth buried in oblivion. It is the most valuable inheritance of the present. It is the essential need of today and the culture of tomorrow".

Yogsanas have a deeper considerable value in the development of the physical, mental and spiritual personality. But pure physical exercises only have effect on the muscles and bones. Aerobic means "with oxygen", and refers to the use of oxygen in the body's metabolic or energy-generating process. [5]

Methods:

This study under investigation involves the experimentation of yoga practice and aerobic exercise on self-confidence and blood pressure (systolic and diastolic). Only middle aged men those who were residing in around Uduppi town, Mangalore District, Karnataka state and aged between 35 and 40 years were selected. The selected thirty subjects were randomly divided into three groups of fifteen each, out of which group - I (n = 15) underwent yogic practice, group - II (n = 15) underwent aerobic exercise training and group - III (n = 15) remained as control. The training programme was carried out for five days per week during morning session only (6 am to 8 am) for twelve weeks. Self-concept was measured with the help of Muktha Rani Rasthogi's self – concept scale and blood pressure was measured by using sphygmomanometer.

Analysis of Data:

The data collected prior to and after the experimental periods on self-concept and blood pressure (systolic and diastolic) on yoga practice group, aerobic exercise group and control group were analysed and presented in the following table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance and 'F' ratio for Self-concept and Blood Pressure (systolic and diastolic) for Yoga Practice Group, Aerobic exercise Group and Control Groups

Variable Name	Group Name	Yoga Practice Group	Aerobic exercise Group	Control Group	'F' Ratio
Self - Concept	Pre-test Mean ± S.D	27.8 ± 0.676	27.4 ± 1.183	2.077 ± 3.14	0.681

	Post-test Mean ± S.D.	29.93 ± 0.961	29.60 ± 1.298	26.60 ± 2.354	18.60*
	Adj. Post-test Mean	29.623	29.662	26.848	40.01*
Systolic Blood Pressure	Pre-test Mean ± S.D	136.73 ± 3.47	135.07 ± 3.654	135.53 ± 2.503	1.05
	Post-test Mean ± S.D.	134.53 ± 3.583	133.87 ± 3.777	137.07 ± 2.434	3.884*
	Adj. Post-test Mean	134.593	134.567	137.307	69.58*
Diastolic Blood Pressure	Pre-test Mean ± S.D	91.40 ± 3.02	90.73 ± 3.28	91.87 ± 1.51	0.659
	Post-test Mean ± S.D.	89.47 ± 2.97	89.53 ± 3.25	92.53 ± 2.031	5.87*
	Adj. Post-test Mean	89.402	90.118	92.014	32.11*

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table value required for significance at .05 level of confidence with df 2 and 43 and 2 and 42 were 3.21 and 3.22 respectively).

Further to determine which of the paired means has a significant improvement, Scheffé *S* test was applied as post-hoc test. The result of the follow-up test is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Scheffé *S* Test for the Difference between the Adjusted Post-Test Mean of Self-concept and Blood Pressure (systolic and diastolic)

Adjusted Post-test Mean of Self-concept				
Yoga Practice Group	Aerobic exercise Group	Control Group	Mean Difference	Confidence interval at .05 level
29.623		26.848	2.775*	0.90898
29.623	29.662		0.039	0.90898
	29.662	26.848	2.814*	0.90898
Systolic Blood Pressure				
134.593		137.307	2.714*	0.8255
134.593	134.567		0.026	0.8255
	134.567	137.307	2.741*	0.8255
Diastolic Blood Pressure				
89.402		92.014	2.612*	0.8512
89.402	90.118		0.716	0.8512
	90.118	92.014	1.896*	0.8512

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

Results:

The training intensity for yogic practice and aerobic exercise was shown in appendices. Before applying the experiment all the subjects of the yoga practice, aerobic exercise and control groups were attended the pre-test, which was conducted a day prior to the commencement of the training and the data were collected on self-concept and blood pressure (systolic and diastolic). After twelve weeks of training the post-test was conducted one day after the training period to find out any changes in the criterion variables.

The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to find out the significant difference if any, among the experimental groups and control group on selected criterion variables separately. In all the cases, .05 level of confidence was fixed to test the significance, which was considered as an appropriate. Since there was three groups were involved in this study, the Scheffé *S* test was used as pos-hoc test and it was shown in Table 2.

After applying the analysis of covariance, the result of this study showed that there was a significant difference among yoga practice, aerobic exercise and control groups on the changes in self-concept and blood pressure after twelve weeks of training. The criterion variables such as, self-concept was improved for both the yoga practice group and aerobic exercise group and systolic and diastolic blood pressure has significantly decreased after the yoga practice, aerobic exercise period. Further, comparing the adjusted post-test means of all the criterion variables, such as, self-concept and systolic and diastolic blood pressure, both the training groups were significantly increased the performance after the training period, when compared with the control

group. Basically the yoga practice and aerobic exercise has tremendously improves the physical, physiological and psychological parameters.

Conclusions:

Self-concept has improved [6] for both the experimental groups, such as yogic practice group and aerobic exercise group, when compared with the control group. The blood pressure has also decreased [6, 7] in yogic practice group and aerobic exercise group when compared with the control group.

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